

SteamBioAfrica Guidelines for Gender-Inclusive Language

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This manual, adapted from the United Nations guidelines for gender-inclusive language, includes a number of strategies to help SteamBioAfrica partners use gender-inclusive language. Gender sensitive communication should be applied to all types of communication including oral or written, formal or informal, or addressed to an internal or external audience.

Some of the strategies to be considered by SteamBio-Africa partners include:

- Taking into account the type of text, context, audience and the purpose of the communication;
- Ensuring that the text is readable and the text clear, fluid and concise;
- Seeking to combine different strategies throughout the text/oral communication.

Gender in English

While there is sometimes overlap between the two terms, ‘sex’ and ‘gender’ usually denote separate concepts. ‘Sex’ is more narrowly defined and is usually based on a spectrum of physiological traits (e.g., chromosomes, hormones, anatomy) present in humans (and some other organisms). Note that, while informed by physical characteristics, the process of defining/assigning sexes (e.g., female, male, intersex) is socially constructed.

In contrast to ‘sex’, ‘gender’ is a more broadly defined concept that refers to the roles, behaviors, activities, and attributes (collectively known as ‘gender norms’) that a given society at a certain time associates with masculinity/femininity/androgyny and with various gender identities (e.g., woman, man, non-binary, trans, gender-fluid). These norms vary in both type and also rigidity. One gender norm may be a loosely observed pattern with little or no moral attachment, while another gender norm may be a strictly enforced taboo, with severe consequences for any individuals who transgress it. The spectrum of gender identities is wide and diverse at both the individual and societal level, and gender norms are constantly shifting alongside other cultural norms.

English has very few gender markers: **pronouns and possessives** (*he, she, they, her, his, their*); and **some nouns and forms of address**. Most English nouns do not have grammatical gender forms (*teacher, president*). A few nouns are specifically masculine or feminine, but it is rarely necessary to use these. For example:

It is not necessary to refer to a woman who acts as an ‘actress’. ‘Actor’ is a gender-neutral term that can be used for individuals of any gender identity (as with ‘doctor’ or ‘editor’).

Instead of using ‘waiter’ or ‘waitress’, one can use the gender-neutral term ‘server’.

Many nouns that once ended in *-man* now have neutral equivalents that are used to include both genders (e.g., *police officer* for *policeman/policewoman*, *spokesperson* for *spokesman*, *chair/chairperson* for *chairman*, *firefighter* for *fireman*). More stereotypical patriarchal representations also include:

Headmaster -School Head, Choirmaster-Choir Director, Sportsmaster-Sports Director, Senior Master/mistress – Senior Teachers.

Where it is necessary to use a gender-neutral pronoun for a unidentified individual, best practice is to use the singular they/them/their. For example:

*“Every Permanent Representative must submit **their** credentials to Protocol.”*

*“Before submitting your document, send it to the focal point for **their** review; **they** will return it to you with comments.”*

Best practices/strategies

A number of strategies can be applied, when speaking or writing in English, to be more gender-inclusive:

1 Forms of address

When referring to or addressing specific individuals, use forms of address and pronouns that are consistent with their gender identity. Often staff members state their preferences on official profiles and staff directories. As such if a staff member appears as “Ms.”, that is the form of address that should be used for her, and she/her pronouns are likely appropriate. However, wherever possible it is best to confirm their preferences before addressing them. Note that some individuals use multiple sets of pronouns (e.g., they/she). Sometimes an individual may most prefer the pronoun listed first, but again, it is best to confirm this with the individual. Some individuals may prefer that both pronouns be used, if possible. (E.g., She received her Master’s degree from Cambridge University in 2014. After graduation, they started working for the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN.)

In cases where there is need to translate drafts the translator should be aware of the gender so that they make use of appropriate terms to use. This is especially important for languages such as Arabic, French, Russian and Spanish.

There should be consistency in the way women and men are referred to: if one of them is addressed by their name, last name, courtesy title, or profession, the other one should be as well.

Gender-sensitive language should be inclusive and below are examples of less inclusive and the preferable way of address:

Less inclusive:**More inclusive:**

“Professor Smith (surname and title for a man) and Madeline (first name for a woman) will attend the luncheon.

“Professor Smith and Professor Jones will attend the luncheon (surname and title for both).”

1.1 Titles, Hierarchy, and Binary

Where possible, it is better not to use any titles at all (i.e., use only given names and surnames). The use of Mr./Ms./Dr./etc. can draw unnecessary attention to those who 1) are non-binary or 2) do not have the same level of education. It is better to avoid this altogether, where possible.

1.2 Ms. or Mrs.?

Care should be taken to use the form of address preferred by each individual. However, when that preference is not known, precedence is given to Ms. over Mrs., as the former is more inclusive and can refer to any woman, regardless of marital status.

Avoid gender-biased expressions or expressions that reinforce gender stereotypes

Discriminatory examples:

- “She throws/runs/fights like a girl.”
- ”Boys dont cry”
- “In a manly way.”
- “Oh, that’s women’s work.”
- “Thank you to the ladies for making the room more beautiful.”
- “Men just don’t understand.”

Less inclusive:**More inclusive:**

“Guests are cordially invited to attend with their wives.”

“Guests are cordially invited to attend with their guests.”

“Fathers babysit their children.”

“Fathers care for their children.”

2 How do I know if I am using discriminatory language?

Reverse the gender: Would reversing the designation or the term from masculine to feminine or vice versa change the meaning or emphasis of the sentence? Would it make the sentence sound odd?

Examples:

- “Women should not seek out leadership positions.”
- “Men cannot do two things at the same time.”

3 Use gender-neutral words

Less inclusive	More inclusive
“Mankind”	“Humankind”; “humanity”; “human race”
“Plans to outsource some 19 services have not proceeded at the anticipated pace, as there are significant manpower shortages.”	“Plans to outsource some 19 services have not proceeded at the anticipated pace, as there are significant staffing shortages.”
“Man-made”	“Artificial”; “human-caused”

4 Use the pronoun ‘one’

Less inclusive	More inclusive
“A staff member in Antarctica earns less than he would in New York.”	“A staff member in Antarctica earns less than one in New York.”
	“A staff member in Antarctica earns less than they would in New York.”

5 Use the relative pronoun ‘who’

Less inclusive	More inclusive
“If a complainant is not satisfied with the board’s decision, he can ask for a rehearing.”	“A complainant who is not satisfied with the board’s decision can ask for a rehearing.”

6 Use a plural antecedent

When referring to generic subjects, plural antecedents may be used in order to avoid gendered pronouns.

Less inclusive

“A substitute judge must certify that **he** has familiarized **himself** with the record of the proceedings.”

More inclusive

“Substitute judges must certify that **they** have familiarized **themselves** with the record of the proceedings.”

“A substitute judge must certify that **they** have familiarized **themselves** with the record of the proceedings.”

7 Omit the gendered word

Less inclusive

“Requests the Emergency Relief Coordinator to continue **his/her** efforts to strengthen the coordination of humanitarian assistance.”

More inclusive

“Requests the Emergency Relief Coordinator to continue efforts to strengthen the coordination of humanitarian assistance.”

“A person must reside continuously in the Territory for 20 years before **he** may apply for permanent residence.”

“A person must reside continuously in the Territory for 20 years before applying for permanent residence.”

8 Use the passive voice

The passive voice is not an appropriate option for all sentences in English, as employing the passive voice often changes the emphasis of the sentence. However, it does offer an option for avoiding gendered constructions.

Less inclusive

“The author of a communication must have direct and reliable evidence of the situation **he** is describing.”

More inclusive

“The author of a communication must have direct and reliable evidence of the situation being described.”

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